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**ANALYSIS OF NON-STATIONARY ELECTRIC DRIVE LOADS IN DRUM SHEARS
BASED ON FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF THE CUTTING PROCESS**

KAIROS NOGAEV

Professor, Karaganda Industrial University, Temirtau, Kazakhstan

ALIBEK BATYRBEK

Doctoral student, Karaganda Industrial University, Temirtau, Kazakhstan

ZOYA GELMANOVA

Professor, Karaganda Industrial University, Temirtau, Kazakhstan

ABDUL WALID FAYEZ WAZANI

Master's degree, Karaganda Industrial University, Temirtau, Kazakhstan

Abstract. *The paper presents a finite element modeling study of the power and energy parameters of the cutting process in drum shears of the 1700 hot rolling mill at QARMET JSC. The relevance of the research is determined by the need to improve the accuracy of load estimation for electric drives of metallurgical equipment operating under variable and impact torque conditions. The simulation was performed in the DEFORM-3D software environment, taking into account thermo-mechanical interaction, nonlinear stress-strain behavior, and the kinematic features of the inter-blade clearance variation.*

As a result, time-dependent characteristics of vertical cutting force, torque, and power were obtained for both the upper and lower drums. It was established that despite similar values of vertical cutting force, the distribution of torque and power between the drums is significantly non-uniform, with the lower drum being subjected to higher loading. The cutting process demonstrates a pronounced non-stationary behavior and the presence of oscillatory components in the final stage, where peak torque and power values are formed.

The study shows that the design and analysis of drum shear electric drives should be based not only on the maximum cutting force but also on the time-dependent torque and power characteristics, which more accurately reflect the real loading conditions. The obtained results can serve as a computational basis for optimizing the structural and operational parameters of drum shears and improving electric drive control systems.

Keywords: *drum shears, modeling, energy-force parameters, program*

Determining the force and power parameters of a technological process is a key stage in investigating the load characteristics of drive motors in metallurgical equipment, since the deformation force, torque, and power consumption are directly related to the actual loading level of the electric drive [1, 2]. Recent studies have shown that predicting rolling force and torque improves the accuracy of process characterization, while accounting for motor loads in individual rolling stands makes it possible to use these data for load balancing, productivity enhancement, and reduction of excessive operating costs [1, 3]. In turn, analyzing the evolution of load torque and motor speed across the stands allows a more adequate assessment of the electrical variables of the drive under actual operating conditions of a metallurgical unit [2]. In this regard, the determination of force and power parameters should be regarded as a necessary scientific and practical basis for the modeling, analysis, and optimization of drive systems in metallurgical equipment [1–3].

This issue is of particular importance for flying shears used in rolling production, where the force and power parameters of the cutting process directly determine the variable and impact nature of the resisting torque on the electric drive shaft. For rotary shears, it has been shown that, at the moment of cutting, a short-term shock cutting torque arises, which may reach values comparable to

the rated motor torque; therefore, maintaining speed stability in the cutting zone becomes an independent task of the drive control system [4]. At the same time, the load imposed on the electric drive is determined not only by the dimensions of the rolled product, but also by a combination of technological factors, including the height of the fracture zone, the length of the cutting line, the critical shear stress of the material, its temperature state, and the cutting angle, since an increase in the cutting angle increases the effective fracture length and, consequently, the required cutting force. Therefore, any change in rolling and cutting conditions is directly transformed into a change in the required torque and motor current of the flying shear drive [5].

It has also been established that the interaction between the electric drive and the elastic multi-mass mechanical system of rotary crop shears causes significant speed oscillations during cutting, operation of the drive under the maximum permissible current for a substantial portion of the cycle, and an increase in the duration of transient processes. This adversely affects cutting quality and increases the requirements for the overload capacity of the motor, the dynamic response of the control loops, and the effectiveness of torque compensation algorithms. One recent study has shown that reducing the amplitude of speed oscillations directly improves the damping of mechanical vibrations and shortens the post-cut transient process [5].

Therefore, when investigating the electric drives of flying shears, the force and power parameters of the cutting process should be regarded as a key input set of parameters for calculating peak currents, assessing overload operating conditions, selecting motor power, and tuning the control system aimed at stabilizing speed and torque during the most heavily loaded phase of the technological cycle. This is consistent with studies in which the application of more accurate torque control in highly dynamic flying shear systems is considered as a means of improving cutting accuracy and reducing current-related emergency shutdowns [4, 6].

Given that the force and power parameters of the flying shear cutting process directly determine the level and nature of electric drive loading, their reliable determination becomes an important computational and analytical task. One of the effective approaches for determining the force and power parameters of cutting is the finite element method, since it makes it possible to investigate the process under conditions that are as close as possible to the actual interaction scheme between the knives and the rolled product. This is particularly important for flying shears, where cutting proceeds under conditions of highly localized plastic deformation and fracture, short-term contact interaction, variable tool kinematics, and pronounced nonlinearity of the stress-strain state. Under such conditions, direct experimental determination of stress, strain, and contact load distributions in the cutting zone is difficult, whereas three-dimensional finite element modeling makes it possible to trace the evolution of the process over time, including the stages of elastic indentation, plastic flow, crack initiation, and final separation of the metal [7, 8].

In this regard, one of the effective tools for the finite element determination of the force and power parameters of the cutting process is the DEFORM-3D software package, which implements the finite element method and enables the simulation of three-dimensional metal processing operations under conditions of large deformation, thermomechanical interaction, and complex contact relationships [9].

The present study considers the finite element determination of the force and power parameters of the cutting process in the DEFORM-3D software environment for the rotary crop shears of the 1700 hot rolling mill at QARMET JSC (Figure 1), which are intended for cropping the head and tail ends of the strip before it enters the finishing stand.

Figure 1 — Rotary crop shears of the 1700 hot rolling mill at QARMET JSC

Particular attention was paid to the cutting process with different knife speeds, in which, during the working rotation of the drums, the inter-knife gap changes sequentially according to the “minus – zero – plus” pattern, thereby ensuring complete metal separation (Figure 2). Taking this kinematic feature into account in finite element modeling makes it possible to determine the time-dependent cutting force, torque, and power, which are required for the subsequent assessment of the loading imposed on the shear electric drives.

	Knife radius	Cutting process			Sheared profile
Differential speed cutting crop shears	 $R_u > R_L$	Knife clearance: g $g < 0$	$g = 0$	$g > 0$	
		1	2	3	
Conventional crop shears	 $R_u = R_L$	$g = 0$	$g > 0$	$g \gg 0$	

Figure 2 — Kinematic schemes of the cutting process

The preparation of the computational model and the numerical simulation of the cutting process were carried out in several stages. The geometric models of the shears and the workpiece were developed in the KOMPAS-3D computer-aided design system (Figure 3) in accordance with the technical documentation of the equipment, after which they were imported into the DEFORM-3D software package for subsequent finite element analysis.

Figure 3 — Geometric model

When formulating the problem, assumptions similar to those adopted in a previously published finite element modeling framework were introduced [10]: the tool was treated as an absolutely rigid body with a constant surface temperature, the workpiece material was considered a homogeneous isotropic medium, and deformation was described within a viscoplastic formulation; the contact interaction was defined using the Siebel friction law.

In the computational model, the workpiece material was specified as AISI 1015 steel. The initial workpiece temperature was set to 900 °C. The contact between the tool and the workpiece was described by the Siebel friction law with a friction coefficient of 0.7. For the drums, angular velocities corresponding to a rotational speed of 46.25 rpm were prescribed, which ensured the reproduction of the required kinematic conditions of the process.

The computational domain was discretized using a finite element mesh comprising 313,578 elements. The numerical simulation was performed in 300 calculation steps with a time increment of 0.001 s. Thus, the total simulated duration was 0.300 s, which was sufficient to reproduce the complete cutting process and to obtain the time-dependent relationships of the investigated force and power parameters (Figure 4).

Figure 4 — Simulation of the cutting process

According to the results of the finite element simulation, the cutting process exhibits a distinctly non-stationary character and is accompanied by abrupt variations in the force and power parameters over time. In the plots of the vertical cutting force (Z) (Figure 5), torque (T) (Figure 6), and power (P) (Figure 7), the “Top die” curve corresponds to the knife of the lower drum with the smaller diameter, whereas the “Bottom die” curve corresponds to the knife of the upper drum with the larger diameter. At the same time, the upper knife has a convex profile, while the lower knife has a concave profile. As a result, during the mutual penetration of the knives and the deformation of the metal, the actual contact surface area, as well as the position of the resultant contact force, differs for each knife at specific moments in time. This leads to similar values of the vertical cutting force, while a pronounced difference is observed in torque and power.

Figure 5 — Vertical cutting force (Z) versus time

Figure 6 — Torque (T) versus time

Figure 7 — Power (P) versus time

Analysis of the Z relationship (Figure 5) shows that up to approximately 0.018–0.020 s, the vertical cutting force remains insignificant, which corresponds to the stage of tool approach and initial contact. This is followed by a sharp increase in the load associated with the active penetration of the knives into the metal and the development of plastic deformation. Within the interval of 0.022–0.035 s, the force reaches a level of approximately $(0.9–1.2) \cdot 10^7$ N, and by the end of the considered segment it increases to maximum values of about $1.5 \cdot 10^7$ N for the knife of the lower drum and $1.6 \cdot 10^7$ N for the knife of the upper drum. The closeness of these values indicates that the vertical component of the cutting force is, in general, borne by both drums in a comparable manner, while its variation is mainly governed by the resistance of the metal to plastic shear and fracture.

At the same time, the T relationship (Figure 6) reveals a substantially more non-uniform distribution of torque between the drums. After the onset of the active cutting phase, beginning at approximately 0.020–0.022 s, the torque acting on the knife of the lower drum increases more intensively and, throughout the main part of the process, exceeds that acting on the knife of the upper drum. In the final stage of cutting, the maximum value for the knife of the lower drum reaches approximately $4.0 \cdot 10^9$ N·mm, whereas for the knife of the upper drum it is about $1.8 \cdot 10^9$ N·mm. Thus, despite the comparable level of vertical cutting force, the torque on the lower drum is more than twice as high. This result is explained by the difference in knife geometry and the resulting asymmetry of the contact interaction: as the contact area and the position of the line of action of the resultant force change, both the load application arm and the ratio of its normal and tangential components vary, which directly affects the magnitude of the torque.

A similar pattern is observed in the P relationship (Figure 7), since at a given angular velocity of drum rotation, the power is determined by the magnitude of the generated torque. During the active phase of the process, the power associated with the knife of the lower drum increases more rapidly and reaches a maximum value of approximately $1.9 \cdot 10^{10}$ N·mm/s, whereas for the knife of the upper drum the peak value is about $8.6 \cdot 10^9$ N·mm/s. Consequently, at the most heavily loaded moment of the process, the energy load on the lower drum is also significantly higher. This leads to the conclusion that, in drive system calculations, the final stage of cutting is the governing one, since it is during this stage that the peak values of torque and power are formed.

It should also be noted that the T and P relationships exhibit an oscillatory character, which is especially pronounced for the knife of the upper drum in the interval of approximately 0.040–0.050 s. These oscillations are associated with the redistribution of contact pressures, changes in the length of the contact line, and the transition of the process from the stage of predominantly plastic indentation to the stage of intense shear fracture of the metal. The non-stationary nature of the loads in this region indicates the variable character of drum loading and confirms the need to account for the time-dependent dynamics of the force and power parameters when analyzing electric drive operation.

In general, the simulation results show that the vertical cutting force varies in a similar manner for both knives, whereas the torque and power are distributed unevenly between the drums. The knife of the lower drum with the smaller diameter is the most heavily loaded in terms of torque and power. Therefore, in the design and verification calculations of the electric drive of rotary crop shears, it is advisable to consider not only the maximum cutting force, but also the peak values of torque and power obtained for the most heavily loaded drum during the final stage of the process.

The obtained results confirm that, in the analysis and design of the electric drive of rotary crop shears, it is insufficient to focus solely on the cutting force. For a correct assessment of drive loading, it is necessary to take into account the entire set of force and power parameters of the process, primarily the time-dependent torque and power relationships, since these most fully reflect the actual operating conditions of the motor. Such an approach makes it possible to improve the reliability of calculations, to justify the selection of drive parameters, and to establish more accurate requirements for the control system.

Thus, the finite element determination of the force and power parameters of the cutting process is an effective tool for investigating the loading of electric drives in metallurgical equipment and may serve as a computational basis for the subsequent optimization of the structural and operating parameters of rotary crop shears.

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